

Paper Chromatography of Metal Ions in Formic Acid-alcohol Systems: Separation of Tin and Antimony from Numerous Metal Ions*

Mohsin Qureshi and Mukhtar A. Khan

Chromatographic behaviour of 29 common cations has been studied in alcohol-formic acid ratios of 9:1, 7:3, 5:5, 3:7, and 1:9. The plot of R_f value of a metal ion against %formic acid provides an S-shaped curve, the R_f value increasing with increase in the acid concentration.

Sn^{2+} and Sb^{3+} show exceptional behaviour. In butanol-formic acid (1:9), these have R_f values ($\text{Sn} = 0.50$; $\text{Sb} = 0.62$) even though most metal ions either 'tail' from the point of application or have zero R_f values. This behaviour and other structural effects have been explained in terms of the polarity of the chromatographic system.

Antimony is one of the metals, separation and determination by paper chromatography of which are rather difficult. We had developed earlier an anisole-formic acid solvent system¹ for the successful separation of Sn^{2+} and Sb^{3+} by paper chromatography. Later, during a study of the separation of various valence states of mercury and antimony, it was noticed that formic acid showed an unusual behaviour with respect to antimony². It was therefore decided to study systematically solvent systems containing formic acid for the paper chromatography of metal ions and to interpret the change in R_f values with change in the nature and composition of the solvent systems used and to develop successful methods for the separation of tin and antimony from numerous metal ions.

Lederer³ described the use of water for separating antimony from common metal ions. This method, however, suffers from some limitations. The concentration of Sb should be rather high, i.e., 0.1 to 0.3 mg. per drop. Even then the separation is not complete and some ions (e.g., Bi^{3+}) are coprecipitated with antimony. Since no other paper chromatographic method for the separation of tin and antimony from numerous metal ions has been reported, an effort has been made to develop such a method.

EXPERIMENTAL

Formic acid (E. Merck, Darmstadt) was used. All other chemicals used were either reagent grade chemicals or these were purified by usual means. Whatman No. 1 paper was used throughout.

*Presented at the first Annual Convention of Chemists, held under the auspices of the Indian Chemical Society in Bombay in December, 1963.

1. Qureshi and Khan, *J. Chromatog.*, 1962, **8**, 276.

2. *Idem*, *Anal. Chem.*, 1963, **35**, 2051.

3. *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1948, **2**, 261.

TABLE I
In methanol—formic acid systems.

Cations.	M ₃ .	M ₄ .	M ₅ .	M ₁ .	Cations.	M ₃ .	M ₄ .	M ₅ .	M ₁ .	M ₂ .	M ₃ .	M ₄ .	M ₅ .
Ag ⁺	0.00	0.00T	0.00 T	0.00T	Co ²⁺	0.00T	0.00T	0.79	0.70	0.76	0.72	0.70	0.84
Hg ²⁺	0.55	0-0.40	0.70TD	0.66	Ni ²⁺	0-0.04	0.73	0.71	0.73	0.60	0.69	0.73	0.75
Hg ₂ ²⁺	0-0.80	0-0.69	0-0.50	0-0.64	Zn ²⁺	0-0.64	0.71	0.70	0.71	0.80	0.68	0.70	0.70
Pb ²⁺	0-0.40	0-0.40	0-0.42	0-0.52	Ca ²⁺	0-0.52	0.76	0.64	0.76	0.70	0.70	0.76	0.70
Cu ⁺	0.71	0.74	0.75	0.69	Ba ²⁺	0.69	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.00	0.58	0.50	0.80
Cd ²⁺	0.60	0.58	0.65	0.40	Sr ²⁺	0.40	0.50	0.54	0.50	0.71	0.55	0.50	0.73
Bi ³⁺	0.63	0.68	0.62	0.57	Mg ²⁺	0.57	0.68	0.70	0.68	0.60	0.62	0.68	0.76
As ³⁺	0.60	0.58	0.53	0.35	Ba ²⁺	0.35	0.85	0.75	0.85	0.80	0.88	0.85	0.85
Sn ²⁺	0.72	0.71	0.81	0.60	V ⁴⁺	0.60	0.72	0.73	0.72	0.60	0.78	0.72	0.74
Sb ³⁺	0.70	0.70	0.75	0.50	Tl ⁺	0.50	..	0.24	..	0.60	0.33	..	..
Al ³⁺	0.80	0.76	0.70	0.72	Tl ⁴⁺	0.72	0-0.80	0-0.80	0-0.80	0-0.85	0-0.70	0-0.80	0-0.78
Fe ³⁺	0.83	0.80	0.76	0.80	Zr ⁴⁺	0.80	0-0.60	0-0.60	0-0.60	0-0.60	0-0.50	0-0.60	0-0.65
Cr ³⁺	0.70	0.66	0.55	0.42	Ce ³⁺	0.42	0.75	0-0.75	0.75	0.81	0.76	0.75	0.86
Mn ²⁺	0.71	0.66	0.64	0.52	V ⁴⁺	0.52	0.71	0.71	0.70	0.68	0.72	0.70	0.76
					La ³⁺	0.52	0-0.70	0-0.80	0-0.70	0.70	0.72	0-0.70	0.74

TABLE II
In n-butanol—formic acid systems.

Cations.	B ₃ .	B ₄ .	B ₅ .	B ₂ .	B ₁ .	Cations.	B ₃ .	B ₄ .	B ₅ .	B ₂ .	B ₁ .
Ag ⁺	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	Zn ²⁺	0.00	0.08	0.38	0.50	0.73
Hg ²⁺	0.00	0.00T	0.41	0.55	0.00T&0.60	Ni ²⁺	0.00	0.65	0.20	0.42	0.72
Hg ₂ ²⁺	0.00	0.10	0.0&0.41	0.0&0.60	0.0&0.60	Co ²⁺	0.00	0.05	0.30	0.50	0.70
Pb ²⁺	0.00	0.00	0.08	0.30	0.51	Cu ²⁺	0.00	0.05	0.28	0.48	0.72
Cu ⁺	0.00T	0.05	0.20	0.32	0.50	Ba ²⁺	0.00	0.00	0.28	0.56	0.80
Cd ²⁺	0.00	0.10	0.22	0.35	0.60	Sr ²⁺	0.00	0.10	0.30	0.60	0.85
Bi ³⁺	0.00	0.10	0.20	0.30	0.30	Mg ²⁺	0.00	0.10	0.30	0.60	0.72
As ³⁺	0.08	0.20	0.18	0.15	0.45	La ³⁺	0.00	0.00	0.00T	0.40	0.70E
Sn ²⁺	0.50	0.55	0.50	0.46	0.62	Ce ³⁺	0.00	0.00	0.00T	0.52	0.70T
Sb ³⁺	0.62	0.60T	0.43	0.40	0.60	Zr ⁴⁺	0.00	0.00	0.00T	0.00T	0-0.8
Fe ³⁺	0.00	0.00T	0.40	0.50	0.76	Tl ⁴⁺	0.00T	0.00T	0.00T	0-0.70	0-0.8
Al ³⁺	0.00T	0.00T	0.25	0.60	0.68	V ⁴⁺	0.00T	0.00	0.50	0.70	0.75
Cr ³⁺	0.00	0.00	0.31	0.60	0.68	Y ⁴⁺	0.00	0.10	0.10	0.30	0.80
Mn ²⁺	0.08	0.10	0.30	0.40	0.70	Ba ²⁺	0.00T	0.20E	0.32	0.66	0.80
						Tl ⁺	0.00	0.65	0.30	0.76	0.72

TABLE III
In allyl alcohol-formic acid systems.

Cations.	A ₃ .	A ₄ .	A ₅ .	A ₂ .	A ₁ .	Cations.	A ₃ .	A ₄ .	A ₅ .	A ₂ .	A ₁ .
Ag ⁺	0.00T	0.00T	0.00	0.00	0.00	Co ²⁺	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.50	0.80
Hg ²⁺	0.00T	0.71	0.00	0.00	0.70	Ni ²⁺	0.00	0.20	0.00	0.61	0.80
Hg ₂ ²⁺	0.00T	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.0 & 0.70	Zn ²⁺	0.00	0.20	0.00	0.50	0.80
Pb ²⁺	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.0 & 0.70	Ca ²⁺	0.00	0.20	0.00	0.52	0.70
Cu ²⁺	0.00	0.20	0.00	0.45	0.69	Ba ²⁺	0.00	0.20	0.00	0.55	0.75
Cd ²⁺	0.00	0.36	0.40	0.67	0.68	Sr ²⁺	0.00	0.22	0.41	0.60	0.70
Bj ²⁺	0.00	0.35	0.40	0.50	0.53	Mg ²⁺	0.00	0.20	0.43	0.60	0.82
As ³⁺	0.46	0.41	0.42	0.40	0.40	Be ²⁺	0.00T	0.15	0.40	0.60	0.82
Sn ²⁺	0.65	0.67	0.57	0.55	0.52	U ⁴⁺	0.00	0.50	0.35	0.54	0.80
Sb ³⁺	0.65T	0.63T	0.63	0.56	0.55	Tl ⁺	0.00	0.30	0.35	0.55	0.77
Al ³⁺	0.00T	0.41	0.57	0.50	0.80	Th ⁴⁺	0.00T	0.00T	0.00	0.60	0.78
Fe ³⁺	0.00	0.63E	0.60	0.65	0.80	Zr ⁴⁺	0.00	0.25	0.32	0.50	0.80
Cr ³⁺	0.00	0.30	0.50	0.60	0.80	Ce ⁴⁺	0.00	0.16	0.20	0.44	0.66
Mn ²⁺	0.00	0.21	0.45	0.60	0.70	V ⁴⁺	0.00	0.30	0.20	0.44	0.66
						La ³⁺	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.60	0.81

TABLE IV
In cyclohexanol-formic acid systems.

Cations.	C ₃ .	C ₄ .	C ₅ .	C ₂ .	C ₁ .	Cations.	C ₃ .	C ₄ .	C ₅ .	C ₂ .	C ₁ .
Ag ⁺	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00T	0.00	Zn ²⁺	0.00	0.10	0.00	0.57	0.68
Hg ²⁺	0.00T	0.00T	0.62T	0.60	0.71	Ni ²⁺	0.00	0.08	0.00	0.46	0.67
Hg ₂ ²⁺	0.00	0.00T	0.0 & 0.60	0.0 & 0.50	0.0 & 0.60	Co ²⁺	0.00	0.08	0.00	0.51	0.71
Pb ²⁺	0.00	0.18	0.0 & 0.20	0.38	0.00 & 0.50	Ca ²⁺	0.00	0.0	0.00	0.50	0.70
Cu ²⁺	0.00	0.10	0.10	0.40	0.52	Ba ²⁺	0.00	0.05	0.00	0.51	0.70
Cd ²⁺	0.02	0.10	0.25	0.45	0.70	Sr ²⁺	0.00	0.00	0.20	0.42	0.72
Bj ²⁺	0.00	0.20E	0.30	0.32	0.00	Mg ²⁺	0.00	0.00	0.10	0.50	0.75
As ³⁺	0.30	0.15	0.52	0.33	0.37	La ³⁺	0.00	0.00	0.15	0.62T	0.71
Sn ²⁺	0.57	0.61	0.65	0.60	0.67	Ce ⁴⁺	0.13	0.08	0.13	0.51	0.55
Sb ³⁺	0.63	0.66	0.62	0.63	0.62	Zr ⁴⁺	0.00T	0.00	0.00T	0.60T	0.70
Fe ³⁺	0.00	0.14E	0.30	0.62	0.73	Th ⁴⁺	0.00	0.05	0.10	0.60	0.70
Al ³⁺	0.09	0.002	0.16	0.53	-0.70	U ⁴⁺	0.00	0.16E	0.25	0.53	0.71
Cr ³⁺	0.00	0.00T	0.20	0.50	0.60	V ⁴⁺	0.00	0.00	0.10	0.40	0.80
Mn ²⁺	0.00	0.08	0.14	0.42	0.70	Be ²⁺	0.10	0.20T	0.22	0.52	0.80
						Tl ⁺	0.00	0.12	0.20	0.60	0.71

The paper chromatography was performed by the ascending technique; 3×15 cm strips were developed in gas jars. Time of conditioning and time of development were respectively 15 and 45 min.

The ions of the H_2S group were detected with yellow ammonium sulphide. Aluminon was used to detect Al^{3+} , Cr^{3+} , Fe^{3+} , Ca^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , and Be^{2+} . Alizarine was used as a spraying agent for La^{3+} , Ce^{3+} , Zr^{4+} , Th^{4+} , U^{4+} , and V^{4+} .

Solvent systems containing the following alcohols were studied: methyl, ethyl, *n*-propyl, isopropyl, *n*-butyl, isobutyl, *n*-amyl, isoamyl, *t*-amyl, allyl, octyl, benzyl, and cyclohexyl. The results are summarised in Tables I-IV. The tables for the remaining nine alcohols have been omitted for the sake of brevity. In the tables the following of abbreviations have been used: M for methanol, B for butanol, A for allyl alcohol, C for cyclohexanol. The alcohol-formic acid ratios used were: (1) 1:9, (2) 3:7, (3) 5:5, (4) 7:3, (5) 9:1.

The ratio numbers are shown in parentheses. The solvent number consists of a symbol to represent the alcohol used with a subscript to denote the ratio number. Thus M_1 stands for methanol-formic acid mixture in ratio number (1), *i.e.*, 1:9; M_2 signifies methanol-formic acid mixture in ratio number (2), *i.e.*, 3:7 and so on. R_f values of 29 common ions in 65 solvent systems are reported.

DISCUSSION

In most cases the plot of the R_f value of a metal ion against the percentage of formic acid in the system provides S-shaped curves (curve a, Fig.1). Very few attempts have been made to study and analyse this behaviour and to correlate the R_f value of a metal ion with changes in the nature and composition of the solvent system. It is true "that polarity, as some workers use it in reference to multi-component systems is some thing of a puzzle". However, if we use two component systems of varying composition, keeping one of the components as fixed, the polarity of the system changes in a systematic manner and the chromatographic results under these conditions show a systematic pattern. Thus if the same acid is mixed with different alcohols, it should be possible to correlate the R_f value of a metal ion with the proportion and the nature of alcohol concerned.

Cassidy⁵ reported that the R_f value of a particular amino-acid followed the order: methanol > ethanol > *n*-propanol = isopropanol > *t*-butanol, which is also the order of dielectric constants of the solvents. We have also found that for systems containing the same percentage of formic acid, the R_f values of most metal ions follow a similar pattern. At low acid concentrations, the R_f values are small because the system is only slightly acidic and because the equilibria involving ionic species are controlled by the acidity of the mobile phase. Low acidity favours the retention of the charged species by the aqueous gel. Taking *n*-butanol-formic acid system as an example, we find that in 9:1 ratio most metal ions either tail or have R_f values close to zero. This is because the small quantity of acid is not

4. Heftmann, "Chromatography", p. 102, Reinhold Publishing Co., 1961.

5. "Fundamentals of Chromatography", Interscience, New York, 1957.

sufficient to check hydrolysis and to form the appropriate ions for migration. Of the 29 metal ions chromatographed, only Sn^{2+} and Sb^{3+} show an exceptional behaviour and have R_f values greater than 0.50. All the cations either tail from the point of application or have R_f values close to zero. This behaviour of Sn^{2+} and Sb^{3+} is probably due to the fact that these form uncharged complexes with formic acid, which have high partition coefficients in non-polar solvents. This unique behaviour of the two cations is further reflected in the fact that as the percentage of formic acid is increased, the R_f values of the two cations remain relatively stationary in all the systems studied (curve b, Fig. 1).

The behaviour of Ag^+ and Hg_2^{2+} also needs some explanation. Ag^+ does not migrate owing to possible reduction. Hg_2^{2+} probably disproportionates. This may be deduced from the fact that frequently Hg_2^{2+} gives rise to double spot formation. One spot has zero R_f value for metallic mercury and the other spot has an R_f value close to that Hg^{2+} .

FIG. 1. R_f values in formic acid—alcohol system. (a) Most metal ions. (b) Sb^{3+} and Sn^{2+} .

FIG. 2. Change in R_f of most metal ions with increase of C atoms in alcohols. 1-8 refer respectively to MeOH, EtOH, *n*-PrOH, *n*-BuOH, *n*-AmOH, and *n*-octyl alcohol.

At low formic acid concentration, e.g. (0-20%), the increase in R_f value with increase in formic acid concentrations is slight due to non-availability of sufficient formic acid to check hydrolysis and to form appropriate ionic species. At high formic acid concentrations (70%), the increase in acid concentration does not significantly change either polarity of the system or the ionic species present. Hence the R_f values do not show a marked change. It is only in the range of 20-70% formic acid concentration that the R_f values of metal ions are most sensitive to the acid concentration and this is reflected in the increase in the slope of the curve. In this way we can qualitatively explain the form of an 'S'-shaped curve.

This general trend is noticeable in almost all systems whatever may be the alcohol used. Methanol is one exception. In this case the R_f values do not change significantly with change in formic acid concentration. The departure from the general behaviour may be attributed to the high D. E. C. of methanol(32.63). Addition of formic acid to methanol does not change significantly the polarity of the system and the R_f values remain almost unaltered.

From the plot of the R_f values against the number of carbon atoms present in various saturated straight-chain alcohols, it is noticed that once again an S-shaped curve is obtained (Fig. 2). In this case, the lower alcohol is more polar and therefore gives rise to a higher

R_f value for the cations. An increase in the number of carbon atoms decreases the polarity of the systems and hence the R_f values also keep on decreasing. When *n*-propanol is replaced by an unsaturated alcohol, like allyl, there is in general an increase in the R_f values owing to the higher dielectric constant of the system. For similar reasons it has been noticed that R_f values are in most cases higher in branched chain alcohols when compared with their straight-chain isomers. Similarly R_f values in benzyl alcohol and in cyclohexanol systems can be explained on the basis of the polarity of the systems. There are a few exceptions to this general trend, which need further study before definite conclusions can be reached.

FIG. 3. Separation of Sn^{2+} with cyclohexanol-formic acid (7:3).

FIG. 4. Separation of Sb^{3+} with cyclohexanol-formic acid system (7:3).

Formic acid-cyclohexanol (3:7) system proved very efficient for the separation of Sn^{2+} and Sb^{3+} from numerous metal ions (Fig. 3 & 4). Separation of binary mixtures containing a particular cation and Sn^{2+} or Sb^{3+} was tried. In each case successful separation was obtained; only Hg^{2+} and Fe^{3+} interfered. Sn^{2+} and Sb^{3+} have R_f values close to 0.65, whereas

other metal ions have R_f values equal to or lower than 0.20. This solvent can therefore be used with advantage for the isolation of tin and antimony from numerous metal ions.

The authors are grateful to Prof. A. R. Kidwai, Head of the Department of Chemistry, for encouragement and research facilities. The financial assistance sanctioned to one of them (M.A.K) by C. S. I. R. is gratefully acknowledged.

CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
MUSLIM UNIVERSITY,
ALIGARE, U.P.

Received August 21, 1964.